

The Effect of Audit Quality, Audit Committee, and Corporate Social Responsibility on Firm Value with Firm Size as a Moderating Variable

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the effect of audit quality, audit committee, and corporate social responsibility (CSR) on firm value, with firm size as a moderating variable. This research employs a quantitative approach using secondary data obtained from the annual financial reports of energy sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The sample was selected using purposive sampling, resulting in 75 observations. The data were analyzed using multiple linear regression and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). The results indicate that audit quality, audit committee, and CSR have a positive and significant effect on firm value. Firm size also has a positive effect and is proven to moderate the relationship between audit quality, audit committee, and CSR on firm value. Additionally, control variables, namely profitability and leverage, are found to have a positive and significant effect on firm value. Simultaneously, all variables in this study significantly influence firm value.

KEYWORDS: audit quality, audit committee, corporate social responsibility, firm size, firm value

I. BACKGROUND

Firm value is a key indicator reflecting a company's performance and investors' perceptions of future business prospects. High firm value is typically indicated by stable and rising stock prices, thereby attracting investors to invest their capital (Saragih & Said, 2023; Mathue et al., 2021; Laksana & Handayani, 2022; Adriani & Parinduri, 2024; Rahmantari, 2021; Lamba & Atahau, 2022; Dina & Wahyuningtyas, 2022; Tandrio & Handoyo, 2023).

In recent years, fluctuations in firm value have remained a common occurrence across various industrial sectors in Indonesia. This situation indicates that firm value is not always stable and is significantly influenced by both external and internal dynamics (Kusmiyati & Machdar, 2023; Rahmantari, 2021; Adriani & Parinduri, 2024; Mathue et al., 2021). One sector significantly affected is the energy sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, which during certain periods experienced a decline in firm value due to global pressures impacting stock prices and economic activity.

Additionally, global geopolitical instability has further exacerbated conditions in the energy sector. International conflicts, such as the war between Iran and Israel, have had a significant impact on global energy supplies, particularly crude oil. This uncertainty has disrupted global energy distribution, thereby triggering a rise in global oil prices. A subsequent impact of this situation is the increase in companies' operational costs, particularly in the mining sector, which is highly dependent on energy fuels.

Based on observations in the energy industry, particularly within the mining sector. The researcher has also directly observed that rising fuel prices—such as industrial diesel, which has increased by nearly 50%—place significant pressure on a company's operational activities. This cost increase not only affects operational efficiency but also has the potential to reduce a company's financial performance, which could ultimately lead to a decline in firm value.

Therefore, this situation indicates that external factors such as global geopolitical dynamics and energy price fluctuations play a crucial role in influencing firm value, particularly within the energy sector. This serves as a critical foundation for researchers to further examine the factors that can influence firm value amid increasingly complex global uncertainties.

One factor suspected of influencing firm value is Corporate Social Responsibility (Rahmantari, 2021; Wijaya et al., 2024; Karina & Setiadi, 2020; Saragih & Said, 2023; Irawan et al., 2023; Rusgowanto & Panggabean, 2021). CSR is a form of corporate responsibility toward the social environment and the surrounding community (Irawan et al., 2023; Rahmantari, 2021; Wijaya et al., 2024; Karina & Setiadi, 2020; Saragih & Said, 2023). Effective CSR implementation is believed to enhance corporate reputation and attract investor interest, thereby leading to an increase in firm value (Karina & Setiadi, 2020; Irawan et al., 2023; Saragih & Said, 2023; Rasyid et al., 2022). However, previous research findings have been inconsistent. Some studies have found that CSR has a positive effect on firm value, while others have shown that CSR has no significant effect.

In addition to CSR, another factor influencing firm value is audit quality. Good audit quality can enhance investor confidence in a company's financial statements; audit quality also reflects an auditor's ability to present reliable financial statements free from material misstatements (Nurhasanah & Napisah, 2024; Purmalita & Fauzan, 2024; Kusmiyati & Machdar, 2023; Adriani & Parinduri, 2024; Septerini & Hendrani, 2024).

Corporate governance mechanisms such as audit committees also play a role in enhancing firm value through oversight of management performance (Safelia et al., 2023; Laksana & Handayani, 2022; Pramestie & Atahau, 2021). As part of corporate governance mechanisms, audit committees also play a crucial role in overseeing financial statements and management performance. The existence of an audit committee can enhance corporate transparency and accountability (Laksana & Handayani, 2022; Pramestie & Atahau, 2021; Safelia et al., 2023). Additionally, firm size is hypothesized to either strengthen or weaken the relationship between independent variables and firm value. Larger firms generally possess more resources and better financing.

Differences in previous research findings and the phenomenon of fluctuations in firm value are important reasons for conducting further research to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing firm value. This study aims to analyze the effects of CSR, audit quality, and the audit committee on firm value, with firm size serving as a moderating variable.

In light of this, this study is expected to provide benefits both theoretically and practically. Theoretically, this study is expected to enrich the literature in the field of accounting, particularly regarding the influence of Corporate Social Responsibility, audit committees, and audit quality on firm value, with firm size as a moderating variable. Additionally, this study can serve as a reference for future research examining similar topics. Practically, this study is expected to provide benefits to various stakeholders. For companies, the results of this study can serve as a basis for consideration in enhancing firm value through the implementation of CSR, improving audit quality, and optimizing the role of the audit committee. For investors, this study is expected to serve as a source of information for investment decision-making by considering non-financial aspects and corporate governance. Meanwhile, for academics, this study can be used as a reference in developing research in the same field.

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Agency Theory

According to Jensen & Meckling (1976) as cited in (Pramudya & Herutono, 2022), agency theory is a concept that explains the cooperative relationship between the company's owners (principal) and the company's management (agent). This relationship arises due to the delegation of authority from the principal to the agent to manage the company and make various operational and strategic decisions.

The relevance of agency theory to this study lies in its role as a foundation for understanding modern business practices. In the context of this study, the relationship between the principal and the agent is crucial because every policy and decision made by management will impact the company's value. Therefore, the implementation of oversight mechanisms such as CSR, audit committees, and audit quality is necessary to ensure that the agent acts in the principal's best interest.

Firm Value

Firm value reflects how investors assess a company based on its book value, as reflected in market prices. In other words, firm value can be defined as the market value of all securities held by the company, which is equivalent to the total of its debt and equity (Mathue et al., 2021; Saragih & Said, 2023; Laksana & Handayani, 2022; Adriani & Parinduri, 2024; Rahmantari, 2021; Selly et al., 2022). The calculation uses the following formula:

$$PER = \frac{\text{Market Price Per Share}}{\text{Earning Per Share}}$$

The Price-Earnings Ratio (PER) serves as an indicator to measure changes in expectations regarding a company's ability to generate profits in the future. The greater the growth potential a company is expected to have by investors, the higher the PER tends to be. This indicates that an increase in PER aligns with the company's growing potential to create future firm value.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a form of a company's commitment to supporting sustainable development,

realized through collaboration among employees, the local community, and society at large (Setiawan & Purwanti, 2021, p. 23; Rasyid et al., 2022; Saragih & Said, 2023). These efforts aim to improve quality of life, drive economic growth, and support sustainable development processes.

In Indonesia, CSR disclosure is regulated by various laws and regulations that require companies to consider social and environmental aspects in all their business activities. This aligns with the concept of sustainable development, where every corporate decision focuses not only on economic aspects but also considers the resulting social and environmental impacts.

In this study, the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) variable is measured by assessing the extent to which companies disclose or mention the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in their financial reports. This measurement aims to identify the company's focus on the sustainable development goals it seeks to achieve. Thus, the more SDG aspects disclosed, the clearer the company's commitment to fulfilling its social responsibilities.

Audit Quality

Audit quality plays a crucial role in influencing the content of audit reports produced by auditors, and can thus serve as an indicator for assessing the reliability and accuracy of a company's financial reporting (Septerini & Hendrani, 2024; Purmalita & Fauzan, 2024; Kusmiyati & Machdar, 2023; Adriani & Parinduri, 2024; Zahrani et al., 2023).

In this study, the audit quality variable is measured using an interval scale that reflects the classification of Public Accounting Firms (PAFs) based on reputation level, operational scope, and international affiliations. This measurement is divided into four categories, namely: (1) small local PAFs, (2) regional PAFs, (3) national PAFs with international affiliations but not included in the Big Four group, and (4) national PAFs affiliated with the Big Four international network. This scale is used to illustrate the differences in audit quality levels, which are assumed to increase as the network, resources, and professional standards applied by each PA firm expand. Furthermore, this measurement approach is supported by prior research, such as that conducted by Brenda et al. (2025) and Winardi et al. (2025), which employed similar classifications in assessing audit quality. By referencing previous studies, the use of this scale is expected to enhance the consistency and validity of the measurement.

Audit Committee

The audit committee is a crucial element and a key requirement for the implementation of *good corporate governance* (GCG). The existence of an audit committee is not merely a formality but is also mandatory for public companies as a form of compliance with regulations set by the Indonesia Stock Exchange and the Capital Market Supervisory Agency (BAPEPAM) (Pramudya & Herutono, 2022; Pramestie & Atahau, 2021). In practice, the audit committee plays a strategic role in assisting the board of commissioners in performing its oversight function regarding the company's operations; the audit committee is also tasked with providing opinions, input, and professional recommendations to the board of commissioners, particularly regarding the effectiveness of the internal control system, as well as various issues of concern to the board of commissioners and reported by the board of directors (Pramudya & Herutono, 2022; Saragih & Tampubolon, 2023).

In this study, the audit committee variable is measured using the number of audit committee members in a company's audit committee. This measurement is expressed in a simple form, namely:

KA = Σ Company Audit Committees

This approach is based on the assumption that the number of audit committee members reflects the company's oversight capacity. The larger the number of audit committee members, the more effective the oversight function is expected to be, due to a more optimal division of tasks, a broader exchange of information, and improved quality of discussion in the decision-making process regarding oversight. The use of this measure is also consistent with previous research conducted by Safelia et al. (2023), which states that the number of audit committee members is a relevant indicator in assessing the effectiveness of the oversight function within a company.

Firm Size

Firm size reflects the scale of a company, which can be observed through equity value, sales, or total assets held (Safelia et al., 2023; Winardi et al., 2025; Selly et al., 2022; Hidayat & Khotimah, 2022). In this study, Firm size derived from financial statements is measured using total assets, which is then expressed as the logarithm of total assets. This proxy was chosen because

it is considered to have a higher level of stability compared to other proxies and is consistent across periods.

Size = Ln (Total Assets)

Hypothesis

1. The Effect of CSR on Firm Value

Based on *Agency Theory*, the disclosure of *Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)* can reduce conflicts between *principals* and *agents* through increased corporate transparency and accountability. Effective CSR implementation can enhance corporate reputation and investor confidence, thereby leading to an increase in firm value. This is supported by research by Karina & Setiadi (2020), Wijaya et al. (2024), and Rahmantari (2021), which shows that CSR has a positive effect on firm value.

Based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H1: CSR has a positive effect on firm value.

2. The Effect of Audit Quality on Firm Value

From the *Agency Theory* perspective, audits serve as a monitoring mechanism to reduce information asymmetry. The use of high quality auditors, such as the Big Four accounting firms, can enhance investor confidence in a company's financial statements. This sends a positive signal to investors, thereby potentially increasing firm value. Previous research findings support this argument. Studies conducted by Purmalita & Fauzan (2024) and Adriani & Parinduri (2024) indicate that audit quality has a positive effect on firm value.

Based on the above discussion, the following hypotheses are formulated:

H2: Audit quality influences firm value.

3. The Effect of the Audit Committee on Firm Value

The audit committee is part of the corporate governance mechanism that plays a role in overseeing management performance. Based on *Agency Theory*, the existence of an audit committee can minimize conflicts of interest between the principal and the agent. An effective audit committee is capable of improving the quality of financial reports and corporate transparency, thereby increasing investor confidence. This increased confidence ultimately leads to an increase in firm value. This is supported by the research of Saragih & Tampubolon (2023), Simandjuntak & Murwaningsari (2022), and Pramudya & Herutono (2022), which shows that audit committees have a positive effect on firm value.

Based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H3: Audit committees have a positive effect on firm value.

4. Firm Size Moderates the Effect of CSR on Firm Value

Firm size reflects the scale of a company, typically measured by total assets. Larger companies tend to have higher levels of public exposure, which encourages them to disclose *Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)* activities more extensively.

The larger the company, the more significant the impact of CSR implementation is expected to be on firm value. This is due to the high level of attention from investors and stakeholders toward large companies, meaning that every CSR activity undertaken is more likely to influence market perceptions and enhance firm value. This statement is supported by previous research conducted by Wijaya et al. (2024), which states that firm size can strengthen the relationship between CSR and firm value.

Based on this discussion, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H4: Firm size moderates the effect of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) on firm value.

5. Firm Size Moderates the Effect of Audit Quality on Firm Value

Large companies have higher operational complexity, thus requiring better audit quality. In large companies, financial statements receive greater attention from investors.

Based on this description, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H5: Firm size moderates the effect of audit quality on firm value

6. Firm Size Moderates the Effect of the Audit Committee on Firm Value

The audit committee is a corporate governance mechanism that plays a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of oversight over management performance. According to Agency Theory, the existence of an audit committee reduces conflicts of interest between principals and agents by increasing transparency and accountability in financial reporting.

In large companies, the level of operational complexity and organizational structure tends to be higher, thus requiring stronger and more effective oversight mechanisms. In this context, the role of the audit committee becomes increasingly crucial as it functions to ensure the quality of financial reports, strengthen internal control systems, and enhance stakeholder confidence. Thus, firm size is hypothesized to strengthen the relationship between the audit committee and firm value. This is supported by the research of Pramudya & Herutono (2022) as well as Simandjuntak & Murwaningsari (2022), which shows that firm size significantly moderates the influence of the audit committee on firm value.

Based on the above discussion, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H6: Firm size moderates the effect of the audit committee on firm value.

The following is a structured framework designed to visually and systematically outline the research to be conducted, namely:

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a quantitative approach with an associative research design aimed at examining the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable while incorporating a moderating variable. The data used in this study are secondary data obtained from the annual reports and financial statements of energy sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). The quantitative method is considered appropriate because this study focuses on testing hypotheses and analyzing the relationship among variables using statistical procedures.

The population in this study consists of all energy sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the observation period. The sampling technique used is purposive sampling, in which the sample is selected based on several criteria. The criteria include energy sector companies listed on the IDX during the research period, companies that publish complete annual reports and financial statements, and companies that disclose data related to the research variables. Based on these criteria, a total sample of 75 observations was obtained.

This study uses Firm Value measured by Price-to-Earnings Ratio (PER) as the dependent variable. The independent variables consist of Audit Quality, Audit Committee, and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). In addition, Firm Size is used as the moderating variable, while Profitability and Leverage are used as control variables.

The data analysis technique in this study uses Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) with the assistance of SPSS software. The analysis is conducted to determine the effect of Audit Quality, Audit Committee, and Corporate Social Responsibility on Firm Value, as well as to examine the moderating role of Firm Size in strengthening or weakening the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The regression model used in this study can be formulated as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 Z + \beta_5 (X_1 \cdot Z) + \beta_6 (X_2 \cdot Z) + \beta_7 (X_3 \cdot Z) + \beta_8 C_1 + \beta_9 C_2 + \varepsilon$$

Tambahan:

- $X_1 \cdot Z$ = Moderasi Kualitas Audit
- $X_2 \cdot Z$ = Moderasi Komite Audit
- $X_3 \cdot Z$ = Moderasi CSR

Hypothesis testing in this study is conducted using the t-test and F-test. The t-test is used to determine the partial effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The decision is made based on a significance level of 5% (0.05). If the significance value is less than 0.05, it indicates that the independent variable has a significant effect on Firm Value. Meanwhile, the F-test is used to determine whether all independent variables simultaneously influence the dependent variable. If the significance value of the F-test is below 0.05, it indicates that the regression model is feasible and that the independent variables simultaneously have a significant effect on Firm Value.

Table of Variables and Their Measurements

Variable	Measurement
Firm Value (Y)	Price Earnings Ratio (PER) = <i>Market Price Per Share / Earning Per Share</i>
Audit Quality (X1)	Classification of Public Accounting Firms : (1) small local PAFs (2) regional PAFs (3) national PAFs with international affiliations but not included in the Big Four group (4) national PAFs affiliated with the Big Four international network.
Audit Committee (X2)	Number of Audit Committee Members
Corporate Social Responsibility / CSR (X3)	Number of SDGs Disclosures in Annual Report
Firm Size (Z)	Natural Logarithm of Total Assets
Profitability (C1)	Return on Assets (ROA) : <i>Earnings Before tax / Total Assets *100%</i>
Leverage (C2)	Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) : <i>Total Liabilities/Total Equity</i>

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Partial Hypothesis Testing (t-Test)

Table of t-Test Results Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	-100.629	32.708		-3.077	.003
	Kualitas Audit	4.126	.360	.617	11.472	.000
	Komite Audit	1.494	.667	.070	2.241	.028
	CSR	.159	.079	.074	2.017	.048
	Ukuran Perusahaan	3.195	.903	.123	3.541	.001

Kualitas Perusahaan	Audit*Ukuran	13.916	5.384	.105	2.585	.012
Komite Perusahaan	Audit*Ukuran	43.336	21.143	.092	2.050	.044
CSR*Ukuran Perusahaan		.231	.086	.129	2.697	.009
Profitabilitas		.940	.218	.157	4.303	.000
Leverage		.482	.083	.214	5.821	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Nilai Perusahaan

Based on the results of the linear regression test, the audit quality variable has a coefficient of 4.126 with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. These results indicate that audit quality has a positive and significant effect on firm value. The higher the audit quality of a firm, the higher its value. This is because high-quality auditors can enhance the credibility and reliability of a company’s financial statements, thereby increasing investor confidence in the company. From an agency theory perspective, audits serve as a monitoring mechanism to reduce conflicts of interest between principals and agents and minimize information asymmetry. Therefore, the use of high-quality auditors sends a positive signal to investors regarding the transparency and quality of the company’s financial information. These findings align with the research by Purmalita & Fauzan (2024), Adriani & Parinduri (2024), Kusmiyati & Machdar (2023), and Septerini & Hendrani (2024), which state that audit quality has a positive influence on firm value.

The audit committee variable has a coefficient value of 1.494 with a significance level of $0.028 < 0.05$, indicating that the audit committee has a positive and significant effect on firm value. This suggests that the more effective the audit committee’s role within a company, the higher the firm’s value. The audit committee plays a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of oversight over management, maintaining the quality of financial reporting, and ensuring the proper implementation of good corporate governance. An effective audit committee enhances corporate transparency, thereby increasing investor confidence in the company. In agency theory, the audit committee serves as a key oversight mechanism to minimize conflicts of interest between management and shareholders. These findings align with the research by Safelia et al. (2023), Pramestie & Atahau (2021), Saragih & Tampubolon (2023), and Pramudya & Herutono (2022), which state that the audit committee has a positive impact on firm value.

The Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) variable has a coefficient value of 0.159 with a significance level of $0.048 < 0.05$, indicating that CSR has a positive and significant effect on firm value. This suggests that the higher the level of CSR disclosure by a company, the higher its firm value. CSR implementation reflects a company’s concern for social and environmental aspects, thereby helping to build a positive corporate image in the eyes of the public and investors. Companies that are active in disclosing CSR are perceived as having a commitment to business sustainability and social responsibility, which in turn enhances stakeholder loyalty and investor interest in investing. These findings support agency theory, which posits that corporate transparency can reduce conflicts of interest and increase investor trust. These findings are also consistent with the research by Karina & Setiadi (2020), Rahmantari (2021), Wijaya et al. (2024), Saragih & Said (2023), and Irawan et al. (2023), which indicates that CSR has a positive impact on firm value.

The firm size variable has a coefficient of 3.195 with a significance level of $0.001 < 0.05$. These results indicate that firm size has a positive and significant effect on firm value. The larger the Firm size, the higher the firm value. Large companies generally have better assets, resources, and operational capabilities compared to small companies. Additionally, large companies tend to be more recognized by investors and the public, thereby enjoying higher market confidence. These conditions enable large companies to secure funding more easily and attract investors, which ultimately enhances firm value. These findings align with the research by Hidayat & Khotimah (2022), Safelia et al. (2023), and Selly et al. (2022), which state that firm size has a positive influence on firm value.

The results of the moderation variable test indicate that the interaction between audit quality and firm size has a coefficient value of 13.916 with a significance level of $0.012 < 0.05$. These results indicate that firm size moderates the effect of audit quality on firm value. This implies that in larger firms, the effect of audit quality on firm value becomes increasingly stronger. Larger companies have higher levels of operational complexity, thus requiring better audit quality to maintain the credibility of financial

reports. The use of high-quality auditors in large companies will enhance investor confidence in the transparency and quality of the company's financial information. These findings align with the research by Nurhasanah & Napisah (2024), which states that firm size can strengthen the effect of audit quality on firm value.

The interaction between the audit committee and firm size has a coefficient value of 43.336 with a significance level of $0.044 < 0.05$. These results indicate that firm size moderates the effect of the audit committee on firm value. In large companies, operational complexity tends to be higher, thus requiring more effective oversight. Therefore, the presence of an audit committee becomes increasingly important in maintaining the quality of oversight, enhancing the effectiveness of internal controls, and ensuring the transparency of the company's financial reports. The larger the company, the stronger the influence of the audit committee on increasing firm value. These findings align with the research by Simandjuntak & Murwaningsari (2022) and Pramudya & Herutono (2022), which state that firm size strengthens the relationship between the audit committee and firm value.

The interaction between CSR and firm size has a coefficient value of 0.231 with a significance level of $0.009 < 0.05$. These results indicate that firm size moderates the effect of CSR on firm value. Larger firms generally receive greater attention from the public, government, and investors regarding their social and environmental activities. Therefore, the implementation of CSR in large firms will have a greater impact on corporate image formation and investor perception. The broader the CSR disclosures made by large firms, the higher the positive market response to those firms. These findings align with the research by Wijaya et al. (2024), Rahmantari (2021), and Rasyid et al. (2022), which state that firm size can amplify the influence of CSR on firm value.

Profitability, as a control variable, has a coefficient value of 0.940 with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. These results indicate that profitability has a positive and significant effect on firm value. High profitability reflects a company's ability to generate profits effectively, thereby sending a positive signal to investors regarding the company's future prospects. The higher a company's profitability, the greater investors' interest in investing, thereby increasing firm value. These findings align with the research by Aziz & Widati (2023), Dina & Wahyuningtyas (2022), and Lamba & Atahau (2022), which state that profitability has a positive effect on firm value.

The leverage variable has a coefficient value of 0.482 with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. These results indicate that leverage has a positive and significant effect on firm value. Effective use of leverage indicates that a company is capable of optimally utilizing external financing to support operations and business development. Additionally, leverage can serve as a signal that the company possesses the ability to manage liabilities and utilize capital effectively to enhance corporate profits. If leverage is managed effectively, this can boost investor confidence and lead to an increase in firm value. These findings align with the research by Aziz & Widati (2023), Lamba & Atahau (2022), and Tandrio & Handoyo (2023), which state that leverage has a positive effect on firm value.

Simultaneous Hypothesis Testing (F-Test)

Table of F-Test Results

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	121.514	9	13.502	126.253	.000 ^b
	Residual	6.951	65	.107		
	Total	128.465	74			
a. Dependent Variable: Nilai Perusahaan						
b. Predictors: (Constant), CSR*Ukuran Perusahaan, Leverage, Komite Audit, Profitabilitas, Ukuran Perusahaan, Komite Audit*Ukuran Perusahaan, CSR, Kualitas Audit*Ukuran Perusahaan, Kualitas Audit						

The F-test results yielded a calculated F-value of 126.253 and a significance level of 0.000 (sig. $0.000 < 0.05$), indicating a significant simultaneous effect. Therefore, it can be concluded that Audit Quality, Audit Committee, CSR, Firm Size, the interaction between Audit Quality and Firm Size, the interaction between the Audit Committee and Firm Size, the interaction between CSR and Firm Size, Profitability, and Leverage collectively have a significant effect on Firm Value.

Coefficient of Determination (R-squared)

Table of Coefficients of Determination (R²)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.973 ^a	.946	.938	.32702
a. Predictors: (Constant), CSR*Ukuran Perusahaan, Leverage, Komite Audit, Profitabilitas, Ukuran Perusahaan, Komite Audit*Ukuran Perusahaan, CSR, Kualitas Audit*Ukuran Perusahaan, Kualitas Audit				

The results of the coefficient of determination test indicate that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.938, meaning that the independent variables account for 93.8% of the variation in the dependent variable, while the remaining 6.2% is attributed to other variables not included in the research model.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that audit quality, the audit committee, and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) have a positive and significant impact on firm value. This indicates that companies with high-quality audits, effective audit committee oversight, and high levels of CSR disclosure are better able to enhance investor confidence and create a positive market perception, thereby increasing firm value.

Furthermore, firm size has also been shown to have a positive influence on firm value and to moderate the relationship between audit quality, the audit committee, and CSR on firm value. Larger firms tend to have better resources, higher levels of transparency, and greater public attention, thereby strengthening the influence of audit quality, the audit committee, and CSR on firm value.

Control variables such as profitability and leverage also demonstrate a positive and significant influence on firm value. High profitability reflects a company’s ability to generate profits effectively, while well-managed leverage can support corporate development and enhance investor confidence. Simultaneously, all independent, moderating, and control variables in this study were found to have a significant influence on firm value.

Based on these findings, companies are encouraged to improve audit quality by engaging reputable auditors and strengthening the audit committee’s functions to enhance the effectiveness of internal oversight. Additionally, companies should consistently improve the implementation and disclosure of CSR to build a positive corporate image and boost investor confidence. For investors, these findings are expected to serve as a basis for investment decision-making by considering not only financial aspects but also audit quality, the effectiveness of the audit committee, and the company’s CSR disclosures. Meanwhile, future researchers are advised to include additional variables that may influence firm value, expand the scope of research to other sectors, and employ different analytical methods to yield more comprehensive and in-depth research results.

REFERENCES

- Adriani, V. A., & Parinduri, A. Z. (2024). Pengaruh Environmental, Sosial, Governance Disclosure, Leverage, Profitabilitas, Ukuran Perusahaan Dan Kualitas Audit Terhadap Nilai Perusahaan. *Innovative: Journal Of Social Science Research*, 4(4), 11817-11829.
- Aziz, M. S. N. H., & Widati, L. W. (2023). Pengaruh Leverage, Profitabilitas, Pertumbuhan Perusahaan dan Ukuran Perusahaan terhadap Nilai Perusahaan. *Journal of Information System, Applied, Management, Accounting and Research*, 7(1), 171-184.
- Brenda, B., Setiawan, T., & Bimo, I. D. (2025). Faktor-faktor yang Memengaruhi Audit Report Lag pada Sektor Consumer Cyclical. *Jesya (Jurnal Ekonomi dan Ekonomi Syariah)*, 8(2), 1505-1515.
- Dina, D. A. S., & Wahyuningtyas, E. T. (2022). Pengaruh Profitabilitas, Leverage, dan Ukuran Perusahaan terhadap Nilai

- Perusahaan (Studi Empiris pada Perusahaan LQ45 di Bursa Efek Indonesia Periode 2018–2020). *Accounting and Management Journal*, 6(1), 36-49.
5. Hidayat, I., & Khotimah, K. (2022). Pengaruh profitabilitas dan ukuran perusahaan terhadap nilai perusahaan sub sektor kimia. *Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi Kesatuan*, 10(1), 1-8.
 6. Irawan, A., Ovami, D. C., Prima, A. P., & Putri, A. P. (2023). Pengaruh corporate social responsibility terhadap nilai perusahaan pada perusahaan perbankan yang terdaftar di BEI. *Bisnis-Net Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis*, 6(1), 341-348.
 7. Karina, D. R. M., & Setiadi, I. (2020). Pengaruh CSR terhadap nilai perusahaan dengan GCG sebagai pemoderasi. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Mercu Buana*, 6(1), 37-49.
 8. Kusmiyati, K., & Machdar, N. M. (2023). Pengaruh Kepemilikan Manajerial, Kualitas Audit, Dan Profitabilitas Terhadap Nilai Perusahaan Dengan Manajemen Laba Sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Jurnal Riset Manajemen Dan Ekonomi (Jrime)*, 1(1), 01-16.
 9. Laksana, N. B., & Handayani, A. (2022). Pengaruh komisaris independen, kepemilikan manajerial dan komite audit terhadap nilai perusahaan dengan kualitas audit sebagai variabel moderasi:(studi empiris pada perusahaan yang terdaftar dalam indeks LQ45 Tahun 2016-2020). *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Politala*, 5(2), 111-129.
 10. Lamba, A. B., & Atahau, A. D. R. (2022). Pengaruh leverage terhadap nilai perusahaan yang dimediasi profitabilitas. *Reviu Akuntansi Dan Bisnis Indonesia*, 6(1), 16-31.
 11. Nurhasanah, I., & Napisah, N. (2024). Pengaruh sales growth, kualitas audit dan opini audit terhadap nilai perusahaan dengan ukuran perusahaan sebagai pemoderasi. *Kompartemen: Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi*, 157-178.
 12. Pramestie, L., & Atahau, A. D. R. (2021). *GCG, Profitabilitas, dan Nilai Perusahaan Asuransi: Efek Moderasi Ukuran Perusahaan* (Doctoral dissertation, Udayana University).
 13. Pramudya, W. H., & Herutono, S. (2022). Perencanaan Pajak, Komite Audit, Nilai Perusahaan Dan Ukuran Perusahaan Sebagai Variabel Moderasi. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Dan Bisnis Indonesia*, 2(4), 991-1002.
 14. Purmalita, M. Y., & Fauzan. (2024). Analisis Pengaruh Kualitas Audit, Struktur Modal, dan Ukuran Perusahaan Terhadap Nilai Perusahaan. *Journal of Trends Economics and Accounting Research*, 4(3), 610-618.
 15. Rahmantari, N. L. L. (2021). Pengaruh Corporate Social Responsibility Terhadap Nilai Perusahaan Dengan Ukuran Perusahaan Dan Profitabilitas Sebagai Variabel Moderasi Pada Perusahaan Farmasi Yang Terdaftar Di Bursa Efek Indonesia. *Jurnal Ganec Swara*, 15(01).
 16. Rasyid, C. A. M. P., Indriani, E., & Hudaya, R. (2022). Pengaruh corporate social responsibility dan struktur modal terhadap nilai perusahaan dengan ukuran perusahaan dan profitabilitas sebagai variabel moderasi pada perusahaan pertambangan. *Jurnal Aplikasi Akuntansi*, 7(1), 136-156.
 17. Rusgowanto, F. H., & Panggabean, R. R. (2021, April). The influence of company characteristics, intellectual capital, and CSR toward company values on companies listed on BEI in 2014 to 2017. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 729, No. 1, p. 012112). IOP Publishing.
 18. Saragih, A. E., & Tampubolon, H. (2023). Pengaruh kepemilikan manajerial, kepemilikan institusional, komisaris independen, dan komite audit terhadap nilai perusahaan pada perusahaan keuangan yang terdaftar di Bursa Efek Indonesia. *Jurnal Minfo Polgan*, 12(1), 1085-1095.
 19. Saragih, A. S. S., & Said, H. S. (2023). Pengaruh corporate social responsibility terhadap nilai perusahaan dengan ukuran perusahaan sebagai variabel moderasi. *Jurnal Akademi Akuntansi*, 6(3), 345-358.
 20. Septerini, B. N., & Hendrani, A. (2024). Pengaruh Kualitas Audit, Kekuatan Pendapatan, Dan Ukuran Perusahaan Terhadap Nilai Perusahaan. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Politala*, 7(3), 615-628.
 21. Setiawan, T., Mathue, M., & Purwanti, A. (2021). Apakah Kekayaan Intelektual dan Pengungkit Keuangan Mampu Menggerakkan Nilai Perusahaan?. *Journal of Business & Applied Management*, 14(2), 139-148.
 22. Setiawan, T., & Purwanti, A. (2021). *Mahir Akuntansi Manajemen: Seri Advance*. Bhuana Ilmu Populer.
 23. Setiawan, T., Selly, L. J., & Harianto, D. (2022). Pengaruh Good Corporate Governance, Profitability, Millennial Leadership, Family Ownership, Dan Firm Size Terhadap Firm Value (Pada Perusahaan Terbuka yang Terdaftar pada Corporate Governance Perception Index Periode 2017-2020). *Journal of Business & Applied Management*, 15(1), 035-048.

24. Simandjuntak, J. B. P., & Murwaningsari, E. (2022). Moderating Effect of Company Size on Audit Committee and Intellectual Capital Toward firm value. *Archives of Business Research*, 10(4), 1-13.
25. Tandrio, G., & Handoyo, S. E. (2023). Pengaruh leverage, profitabilitas, dan kebijakan dividen terhadap nilai perusahaan. *Jurnal Manajerial Dan Kewirausahaan*, 5(1), 20-27.
26. Wijaya, Z. I. M., Suharsono, R. S., & Afroh, I. K. F. (2024). The Influence of CSR, Profitability and Leverage on Company Value with Company Size as a Moderator. *Finance: International Journal of Management Finance*, 2(1), 33-44.
27. Winardi, J. C., Setiawan, T., & Kuswanto, R. (2025). Faktor-Faktor Yang Memengaruhi Audit Delay, Dimoderasi Ukuran Perusahaan Dan Reputasi KAP. *Jurnal Ekonomi Bisnis, Manajemen dan Akuntansi (Jebma)*, 5(1), 226-238.
28. Zahrani, K., Mappadang, A., & Mappadang, J. L. (2023). The Effect of Capital Structure, Profitability, and Audit Quality on Company Value with Company Size as a Moderation Variable. *International Journal of Asian Business and Management*, 2(6), 1039-1060.
29. Zahwa, A., & Safelia, N. (2023). Pengaruh Good Corporate Governance Terhadap Nilai Perusahaan dengan Ukuran Perusahaan Sebagai Variabel Moderasi (Studi Empiris Sektor Perbankan yang Terdaftar di Bursa Efek Indonesia Tahun 2019-2021). *Jurnal Akuntansi & Keuangan Unja*, 8(2), 155-169.

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